

eties. After 48-hours inoculation in a saturated-moisture atmosphere at 28-30°C, 40 seedlings of each variety were transplanted at 10 seedlings/pot. Pots

were placed under partly-shaded condition, 80-90% relative humidity, and temperature 28-30°C. At 30 days after inoculation, all varieties were infested

(see table). Seven varieties had severe infestations (disease incidence 61-78%); 24 varieties, moderate (45-60%); and three varieties, slight (26-39%). ■

Tungro-tolerant rice varieties for second crop

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Normally second-crop rice in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, is sown from 15 August to 30 September. The yields of 140- to 160-day varieties are adversely affected by epidemic rice tungro disease.

Four rice varieties — two Pankaji Jagannath (IET5852 and IET5897), one CR70-80-2/ Pankaj (IET5890), and one Pankaji Vijaya (IET6262) were compared to TN1 susceptible check and IR20 during 1979, a year when tungro occurred naturally, and 1980, a year when green jassids were kept under check (see table).

The parents of the hybrid derivatives

Grain yield and tungro disease score of 4 second-crop varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Variety	1979		1980	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tungro disease score
CR 70-80-2/Pankaj IET589 (CR213-1002)	3.4	5	4.8	3
Pankaj/Jagannath IET5852 (CR210-1005)	4.1	5	4.2	3
IET5897 (CR210-1009)	4.3	3	6.6	3
Pankaj/Vijaya IET6262 (CR262-16)	4.0	1	4.6	nil
TN1 (susceptible check)	0.5	9	0.7	9
IR20	2.2	5	3.8	3

^aScore chart scale (% hills infested):

- 1 less than 1%
- 3 about 10%
- 5 about 30%
- 9 about 100%

— Pankaj, CR70-80-2, Jagannath, and Vijaya — have tungro and green jassid resistance. IET5897 (CR210-1009 of Pankaj/Jagannath) consistently regis-

tered high yields during both years. The variety IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya) had a higher degree of field tolerance for rice tungro. ■

Evaluation of rice mutants resistance to thrip

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Rice thrip *Thrips oryzae* Williams is generally considered a minor pest of rice in Bangladesh. The only species so far recorded in Bangladesh, its populations recently have assumed economic significance in some areas. Infestations occur in early growth stages of rice plants. Both nymphs and adult thrips damage rice plants by lacerating the leaf-tip

Rice mutant resistance to thrip at Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Mutant, variety	Leaf infestation ^a (%)	
	Summer 1981	Autumn, 1981
Mut 1-1	9.50 a	2.43 a
Mut 1-2	8.18 a	0.43 a
BR3	21.48 c	
IR8	19.02 bc	5.84 b
IRATOM24	18.59 bc	3.57 ab
IRATOM38	18.06 b	—

^aIn a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

tissues and sucking the sap. The infested plants appear to suffer from water stress. Infested leaves roll and yellow. In heavy infestations, the leaf-tips wither

and the plant wilts.

Two early-maturing mutants, Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 originally isolated from IR8 after gamma-irradiation, with the mother variety and checks BR3, IRATOM24, and IRATOM38 were assessed for rice thrip resistance. Experiments in summer and autumn, 1981, used a randomized block design with four replications. The infested leaves in 10 randomly selected hills in each plot were counted.

Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were found to be moderately resistant to thrip, but varieties BR3, IR8, and IRATOM38 were susceptible (see table). ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Green leafhopper resistance and tungro infection in IR varieties

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Varieties developed at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and evaluated by the seedling bulk test (SBT) exhibited different levels of *Nephotettix virescens* resistance. *N.*

virescens damages the rice plant directly and is a very efficient vector of rice tungro virus. To determine the degree of tungro resistance in varieties IR5 to IR54, 20-day-old seedlings of the test